

CONCEPTUAL DESIGN OF GASIFIER PROCESSING HEAVY OIL FRACTIONS

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Abstract

Maximization of material and energy efficiency is imperative for the refining and petrochemical industries to succeed on the competitive market. Searching for suitable solutions, refineries often focus on the “bottom of the barrel”, striving to upgrade the heavy oil residues from hydrocracking processes. Such materials are typically sold as low-cost ship fuels or serve for internal heat and power production. One of the possible alternatives is to route such feedstock to a gasifier, where it is broken down into small molecules with the help of a suitable gasifying agent (air, oxygen, steam). Gasifier effluent is then treated in a series of steps, optimized for its energy content recovery as well as for removal of undesired fractions (tars). The produced cleaned syngas is suitable as fuel or can undergo further treatment to recover hydrogen or other valuable components. This study presents the results of a conceptual design of a gasifier processing heavy oil fractions. Advantages of integrating the gasifier within a refinery are pointed out.

Introduction

Heavy oil residues belong to refining by-products with lower value, usable as ship fuels or as calorific fuels for steam and power plants. This material consists of large hydrocarbon molecules (asphaltenes) with heteroatoms embedded in their structure¹ and is difficult to be upgraded with conventional refining techniques. Its material utilization by thermochemical conversion^{2,3} poses a challenge but is, on the other hand, a promising means for increasing its market value^{4,5}, especially if its use as fuel would be banned due to environmental regulations becoming steadily more stringent.

Gasification is a promising alternative to valorize various liquid and solid by-products and wastes by converting them into syngas⁶ which, on being cleaned, can further be utilized as a source of hydrogen⁷, or for highly efficient heat and power cogeneration^{8,9}. Coal, biomass, or various waste fractions represent just a part of possible feedstock for gasification units¹⁰⁻¹². Gasifying agents include air, steam and/or oxygen^{9,13}. Syngas cleaning is considered as one of the crucial issues impacting the viability of gasifiers¹⁴, its design being still case-dependent and, despite a lot of research undertaken¹⁵, still incurring significant operational expenses to the plant^{16,17}.

Standalone thermochemical feedstock valorization projects (either by pyrolysis or gasification) cope with a multitude of issues to comply with the related legislation, leading to extra capital investment and operation expenses to deal with all by-products and wastes generated in the process¹⁸. In addition, their social acceptance is usually low¹⁹ which repeatedly prevented such units to be built either in Slovakia or elsewhere in Central Europe. On the contrary to that, incorporating a gasifier in an existing industrial enterprise poses a possibility to exploit its existing infrastructure²⁰ and spare capacities of auxiliary units capable to clean the produced syngas and wastewaters. Moreover, material and heat integration are made possible which, taken altogether, should lead to a decrease in capital expenses and an increase in revenue of gasification projects due to exploited synergies²¹.

This is a pilot study focusing on heavy oil residues gasifier unit design, to be placed in an existing refining complex^{22,23}. Possibilities for plant integration are pointed out along with utilization of the spare capacities of plant's gas desulphurization systems. Further research will aim at techno-economic studies comparing standalone and integrated gasification plants.

Materials and methods

Typical heavy oil residue gasification plant integrated in oil refinery consists of three main blocks, that are coupled together. Considered process flow diagram is shown in Figure 1. The main three blocks are block of heavy oil residue gasification and syngas generation, block of syngas cleaning and cooling and block of steam and power generation. Syngas generation block includes oxygen compressor (**KOM**) and gasification reactor (**REA**). Syngas cooling and cleaning block includes heat exchanger and condenser joined in series (**VT6**, **VT7**), section of acid gas absorption and regeneration of absorbent (**ABS**, **DES**) and PSA section (**PSA**). Steam and power generation block includes steam boiler (**KOT**), deaerator (**ODP**), condensate and fresh chemically treated water

preheaters (VT4, VT5) and steam condensation turbine with power generator (KPT). Main material and energy inputs and outputs are heavy oil residues (T1), oxygen (O1), chemically treated water (U1, U2, U3), return condensates (K4), hydrogen gas (G12), PSA off-gas (G11), steam export (P12) and produced power. Waste gas from acid gas adsorption is rich in H₂S (G7) and was not considered in overall energy balance.

Figure 1. Considered flow diagram of heavy oil residue gasification plant

Flow scheme of reactor is shown in Figure 2. Type of reactor considered in this study is entrained-flow reactor, that was approximated as CSTR reactor with perfect dispersion (spray) of heavy oil residue.

Figure 2. Flow scheme of reactor (1 – Heavy oil residue, 2 – Compressed oxygen, 3 – Steam with pressure reduction, 4 – Ash, 5 – Syngas)

Composition of heavy oil residue depends on oil composition², therefore, reactor processing rate of 60 t/h was assumed. Heavy oil residue's w composition (mass %) and LHV (lower heating value, MJ kg⁻¹) is shown in Table I.

Table I
Heavy oil residue properties²⁴

Dry heavy oil residue					Ash	Moisture	LHV
C	H	O	N	S			
86.25	11.05	0	0.40	2.20	0.10	0.30	40.5

Further assumptions include the following quantities and qualities of single inlet flows and process parameters of reactor, shown in Table II.

Table II

Process parameters (* – preliminary results)

Parameter	Value	Reference
t_1 , °C	200	25
t_2 , °C / P_2 , MPa	415.6 / 3	*
t_3 , °C / P_3 , MPa	460 / 6	*
$m_1 : m_2 : m_3$	1 : 1.1 : 0.35	26
P_{reactor} , MPa	3	26
τ_5 , s	12	27
w_5 , m s^{-1}	1.5	23

As the pressure of inlet steam is higher than pressure in gasifier, isenthalpic pressure reduction is also needed (from 6 MPa to 3 MPa). Complete conversion of carbon was assumed; reactions of gasification are presented in equations (1) – (5)^{2,26}.

Reactions (1) – (3) are deemed to be instant, reaction rates of (4) and (5) are presented in equations (6) – (9)^{25,28}.

$$r_4 = 2700 \exp\left(-\frac{1510}{T}\right) \left[C_{\text{CO}} C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}} - \frac{C_{\text{CO}_2} C_{\text{H}_2}}{K_{C4}} \right] \quad (6)$$

$$K_{C4} = 0.0265 \exp\left(\frac{3968}{T}\right) \quad (7)$$

$$r_5 = 1.585 \times 10^7 \exp\left(-\frac{24157}{T}\right) \left[C_{\text{CO}} C_{\text{H}_2} - \frac{C_{\text{CH}_4} C_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}}{K_{C5}} \right] \quad (8)$$

$$K_{C5} = T^{-6.567} \exp\left(\frac{7082.848}{T} + \frac{7.466 \times 10^{-3}}{2} T - \frac{2.164 \times 10^{-6}}{6} T^2 + \frac{0.701 \times 10^5}{2T^2} + 32.541\right) \quad (9)$$

Reactor dimensions are calculated via equation (10).

$$\dot{V}_5 = \frac{V_R}{\tau_5} = \pi D_R^2 w_5 = \frac{\pi D_R^2 L_R}{4\tau_5} \quad (10)$$

Discussion and result analysis

This system represents a set of several non-linear equations, that consist of material balances of each component, overall enthalpy balance and reactor size equation, what was solved by using MATLAB. Results are shown in Table III.

The results indicate that outlet syngas is energy-rich, which can be further utilized. Main components of syngas are hydrogen and carbon monoxide. Considering the acid gas content, mainly H₂S, it is necessary to separate these gases out of the syngas, otherwise they would act corrosively. Simultaneously, rapid syngas flow in reactor entrains solid phase pieces (mainly tars, soot, heavy metals), which can shorten the equipment's life in operation and solid phase separation is also necessary. Reactor is 18 m high, and its diameter is 3.1 m, representing reactor volume 134.3 m³.

Table III

Results of calculations (# - physical enthalpy, reference conditions: 0°C, gaseous state)

Parameter		Value
n_s , kmol s ⁻¹		2.44
t_s , °C		1 384
P_s , kPa		3 000
Composition, mol. %	H ₂ O	7.51
	CO	46.11
	CO ₂	2.40
	H ₂	41.88
	CH ₄	0.33
	N ₂	1.29
	H ₂ S	0.47
h_s , kJ kmol ⁻¹ #		45 656
LHV, MJ kmol ⁻¹		236.9

Main product of gasification is hydrogen, most frequently. As was mentioned, component separation is needed, preceded by syngas cooling and vapour condensation. First of all, solid phase pieces are separated using cyclone, then syngas physical energy content is utilized by high pressure steam production, that can be coupled with cogeneration. Before acid gas absorption is used, syngas temperature must be further decreased by cooling (and simultaneous vapour condensation) using water injection and subsequent tubular heat exchanger. Acid gas absorption unit is coupled with absorbent regeneration section. Chemisorption by alkaline absorbents is used, mostly employing aqueous solutions of alkanolamines. Last step of hydrogen production is its separation from purified syngas. This operation can be realized by membrane or cryogenic separation, but most conveniently by adsorption. Because of many components, PSA adsorption is used. Products of this process are high purity hydrogen and PSA off-gas, further used as fuel.

Summer and winter regime are distinguished in plant's operation. Winter operation enables excess steam export to the refinery with steam condensates return assumed. In this regime, steam turbine minimizes the share of condensing power production; thus, it lowers its electric output to generate low pressure steam for export instead. In summer, steam export option is not considered, and all excess steam is used to produce electric energy surplus. Individual features of both operation regimes can be followed in Table IV showing the obtained energy balance of the gasification plant.

Table IV

Proposed energy balance of the gasification plant in summer and winter regime

Energy content, MW	Winter	Summer
Feeds		
VR	676	676
Oxygen	1	1
Chemically treated water (U1)	2	2
Return condensates (K4)	7	0
Products		
Hydrogen (G12)	186	186
PSA off-gas (G11)	389	389
Excess electric energy	8	18
Steam export	59	0
Losses and waste streams	44	86

Polygeneration operation with steam export in winter lowers the production of waste heat. Waste heat production in summer as almost twice compared to winter, mostly due to condensing turbine steam condenser load.

Conclusions

Purpose of this study was to estimate basic design and operation parameters of HOR gasification reactor processing 60 t/h of HOR. The obtained syngas represents a source of usable materials (as hydrogen) as well as a source of technically usable energy for cogeneration. Locating the gasifier in existing oil refinery enterprise with existing infrastructure and spare capacities for syngas and wastewaters cleaning can enhance the gasification plant's flexibility and make it an environmentally friendly method of vacuum residue valorization following the concept of polygeneration. Apart from hydrogen, the plant exports both calorific offgases, excess electric energy and excess steam (in winter). The possibility of offgases and steam export to the refinery improves the plant's energy efficiency substantially and is expected to improve its economic feasibility, compared to a standalone gasification plant. This will be subject of further research.

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